

UNDERSTANDING HONOUR KILLING: EXPLORING THE PSYCHOSOCIAL FACTORS AMONG PASHTUNS IN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

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ABSTRACT

A major aim of this study is to explore the psychosocial effects of honour killings on society and psychological well-being among Pashtuns living in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, especially mental health and social harmony among them. According to the inclusion criteria used in the current study, a purposive sampling method was used to select participants. This qualitative study aimed to explore the perceptions and thinking processes of 14 participants from different villages through semi-structured interviews to better understand their perceptions and thought processes. All the data was then transcribed, analysed, and interpreted following the steps of thematic analysis. A total of seven major themes emerged because of the data analysis. There are certain kinds of cases that can have a significant negative impact on an individual's mental health and disrupt their social stability when they witness or hear about them. Additionally, honour killings are mainly caused by tarnishing family reputations and land disputes. According to these findings, cultural and socioeconomic factors contribute to honour killings and should be addressed by policymakers. Educational programs that promote gender equality and conflict resolution may help reduce such incidents. Furthermore, developing mental health support systems for communities affected by these events is crucial to restoring social harmony and improving psychological well-being.

Keywords: Honour killing, psychological well-being, psychosocial factors, patriarchal societies, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Introduction

Honour killing, a concept deeply ingrained into the social fabric of society, refers to the killing of anyone, usually a woman, by family members who perceive the actions as dishonourable and take matters into their own hands to restore their reputation. According to the 2004 Act, karo kari (honour killings) are considered murder with penalty provisions. The government has viewed this as a demonstration of its determination to eliminate honour killings

and violence against women. An honour crime refers to the killing or harm inflicted on people, usually women, to protect their honour. The following is a simplistic definition of "honour" killings that when a man kills a woman and claims that she committed immoral acts, it is called "honour killing", not "murder" (Ali, 2001). Alternatively, honour crimes may be defined as acts of violence, most commonly murder, committed by male family members

against female family members who have damaged the family's honour (Lari et al., 2011) Honor killings are caused by a variety of factors, including land disputes among families, unfaithful partners, love marriages, running away from home, perceived immodesty, and suspicions based on false accusations. It is the contention of the World Health Organization (2022) that mental health is the state of a person's mental well-being, and a disturbance of this state has been linked to honour killings in the community. This would have a negative impact on the societal equilibrium in a variety of ways, which will lead to social instability. There is a difference in gender norms, community pressure, as well as tension between generations. The practice is commonly observed in patriarchal societies throughout the world, in which men, including younger boys, hold influential roles and take the community forward (Malik et al., 2023). Taking into consideration the notable Pashtunwali of the Pashtuns, which is their Code of Honor and known as their way of life, is a constitution that highlights eleven principles, of which one is Nang, which is regarded as highly valuable within the culture. Family and property are protected by the protection of dignity and honour (Habib et al., 2023).

There are several research studies that have shed light on honour killing in Pakistan as more people are becoming aware of this issue. The research suggests that honour killings occur when societal norms and cultural expectations have been violated by both men and women (Malik et al., 2023) Statistically, honour killings have decreased from 590 cases in 2022 to 346 cases in 2024 (Haider, 2024). The honour killings are a major issue across the globe; however, they do occur in Pakistan as well. This practice is often justified as a means of restoring family honor, especially among women. Honour killings generally occur on the outskirts of Pakistan, but can also occur in tribal areas, where conservative viewpoints encourage this practice. Many factors contribute to the suffering of the victims and their families, including fears of dishonour that further lead to their submission to societal rules and expectations (Nawaz et al., 2022).

Honour killings are perpetuated in part by cultural norms that enforce rigid gender roles and expectations. A culture of silence and complicity results from these norms, which often prioritize the honor of the family over that of the individual. Thus, victims and their families may feel pressured to conform to these societal standards, even at the expense of their personal safety. In Pakistan, honour crimes have been increasing uncontrollably and are, regrettably, widely accepted by society. In honour crimes, victims range in age from newborns to elderly women, regardless of whether they are married, single, or live in a rural or urban setting. A major reason for the alarming increase in honour crimes is the lack of punishment for the perpetrators of these crimes, as they often escape accountability. Pakistan has a low rate of reporting these crimes; even when they are reported, offenders often receive lenient sentences rather than the severe penalties they deserve, which has a significant impact on the judicial system (Kanwal, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

There have been several psychological and sociological theories developed and incorporated into this study to understand honour killing in Pakistan, specifically in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. It is through the theoretical framework that we will gain insight into why people commit honour killings.

Cultures are inherently valid and can only be fully understood within their unique contexts (Cassar, 2022). Honour killing is considered acceptable in some cultures as a response to perceived dishonour, such as engaging in premarital relationships or rejecting an arranged marriage. According to supporters of cultural relativism, these practices are deeply rooted in tradition and should not be subject to criticism by outsiders. In contrast, this view is problematic because it can justify severe human rights violations and violence against women, especially in the name of preserving culture. While cultural relativism promotes tolerance and understanding, it raises serious ethical concerns when used to justify behavior that violates individuals' rights and perpetuates violence against women.

Honour-based Social Identity (Henri-Tajfel & Turner, 1979) theory primarily focuses on explaining how social conditions and cognitive processes contribute to intergroup behaviors, such as prejudice, bias, and discrimination, which are related to these phenomena. The study suggests that people seek to enhance their self-esteem by identifying with in-groups and differentiating themselves from out-groups (McLeod, 2023).

It is possible for groups to take extreme measures to restore their collective identity when they perceive their reputation to be threatened. To restore the family's reputation within the wider community, they might engage in violence motivated by honour, which can include acts such as honour killings.

Frustration-Aggression Theory (Dollard et al., 1939) can help explain why family members react violently when a woman's actions are perceived as challenging the norms of the family and as compromising the reputation of the family in patriarchal cultures. The women's actions threaten the honour of the family, which leads to violent actions because of the male pressure due to family's respect. It is suggested in this theory that frustration leads to aggressive behavior and reactions, particularly when an individual's purpose-driven actions are hindered. According to the frustration-aggression hypothesis, frustration can serve as a precursor to aggressive behavior, clarifying the social and psychological factors that influence an individual's responses to frustration (Tan, 2042). According to moral disengagement (Bandura, 1999), people justify their immoral behavior by changing their reasoning to avoid feeling guilty. Predictably, there are differences in the social sanctioning and use of violent means across regions because moral justifications are based on a subcultural code of honour (Cohen & Nisbett, 1994). Family members who support or carry out honour killings do not view their actions as cruel. Instead, they rationalize them as a responsibility to preserve family honour, employing methods such as moral justification ("It was necessary to maintain our reputation").and euphemistic labelling ("It was an act of love"). It is through these cognitive frameworks that they can perceive their actions

to be morally acceptable, thereby reducing cognitive dissonance and enabling them to justify their behavior within their cultural and social context.

Rationale

The purpose of this study is to understand the psychological and social factors that can influence the environment in a way that prevents honour killings from happening. Cultural norms, family dynamics, and community attitudes play a key role in either sustaining or stopping violence of this kind. To develop effective interventions and prevention strategies, this study examines these factors.

First, it should be noted that both genders are at a disadvantage when it comes to understanding honor killing. There is a great deal of emphasis on women being the victims of this practice, so much so that sometimes there is no consideration for the psychological aspects of the victims' loved ones because of this practice. Additionally, there is limited knowledge about what the long-term effects of these incidents are for children who have witnessed such encounters in the past. The mental health consequences of growing up in a situation like this can be devastating, such as creating anxiety, fear, or PTSD in the young adults of KPK Pashtuns. A further problem is that not enough is known about the psychological impact that honour killing has on a community because studies tend to focus on the honour killings and their details rather than on the potential mental health implications that honour killing may have. The honour killings are often perpetuated by factors such as rigid gender roles, patriarchal structures, and cultural traditions. A woman's behavior is expected to uphold certain standards in many cultures, particularly in those that place a high value on family reputation. This societal pressure can lead to extreme measures when perceived violations occur, highlighting the need for a deeper understanding of these cultural dynamics to address and prevent such practices.

Method

The study uses a qualitative method to gather in-depth insights into the issue of honour killing. This research strategy is centered on understanding people's perceptions, attitudes, experiences, and meanings so that we can have a better understanding of the phenomena. Qualitative research delves into the rich textures of human experience and perspective, capturing contexts and nuances often lost in numerical translation (Lim, 2024).

Objectives

The main objective of this study was to examine how cultural norms and traditions influence the justification of honor killings in Pashtun society. A study of gender differences in expectations and responsibilities in relation to family honour was conducted as well. Finally, it was also discovered that honour killings have psychological consequences for the immediate family of the victim. The purpose of this study is to identify the role that education plays in influencing attitudes toward honour-related violence.

Research Design

The purpose of the study was to explore the perspective of Pakistani culture, especially that of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. An exploratory research design was used to better understand the viewpoint of Pakistani culture, primarily from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. It is employed to investigate a problem that has not been previously identified. It aims to gain insights, identify patterns, and establish a foundational understanding of the topic (Hassan, 2024).

Measures

Semi-structured interviews were used to gather information about participants' perspectives on honour killing. In this method, the interviewer listens to the participants' stories carefully and records his/her understanding of them to gain the perceptions, thoughts, and ideas of the individuals (Taherdoost, 2022). Firstly, a demographic questionnaire was used to get background information about the participant, including their area of belonging, which plays a key role in the research. There were twenty semi-

structured questions which used as a guide to ask all the necessary questions. Moreover, a field observation report was made, noting down the non-verbal cues and behaviours that were observed.

Participants

Purposive sampling was used in the study. It is a technique in which participants are added to the research based on some inclusion criteria. Purposive sampling refers to a group of non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have characteristics that you need in your sample (Nikolopoulou, 2022). The study included participants of Pathan ethnicity from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. A total of 14 individuals voluntarily took part in this study. An inclusion criterion was established that filtered the individuals who could partake in the study, which included two major facets. Firstly, they had to be part of the Pashtun culture, only then they could voice their opinions and answer the questions regarding the psychological impacts, and second, they had to have witnessed or heard of an honor killing case to gain firsthand insights into the practice. There were 5 males and 9 females between the ages of 20-54. While most of the participants were educated, the sample also included some individuals with lower levels of education. Prior to conducting the interview, informed consent was taken from every participant, ensuring no psychological harm, and they were fully briefed about the purpose of the research. On average, each interview lasted approximately for about 14 minutes, and were conducted in Urdu and Pashto, depending on which language they were more comfortable in while giving the interview.

Procedure

Based on the literature review, a semi-structured interview guide was constructed using inductive reasoning. The feasibility of the research was assessed through a pilot test before conducting the actual interviews. A pilot test can be viewed as a rehearsal before the main performance, providing an opportunity to ensure that all items will function as intended and as anticipated (Wagle, 2021).

The researchers travelled to Peshawar to interview people regarding their perspectives on honor killing cases. The Pashtuns were the target population for this study to gain their insight into this issue. The first site visited was a school at which females from various departments were approached. Each interview began by building a rapport with the candidate so that he or she could feel at ease and comfortable so that they were able to answer the questions honestly. During the interview process, all participants were informed of the purpose of the study, and written consent and responses would remain confidential and anonymous, and only be used for research purposes. The purpose of conducting interviews was explained to them as well as the topic of discussion. Before the interview, consent was obtained from participants. The interview lasted approximately 20 to 30 minutes. According to the language preferences of the participants, the interviews were conducted in Urdu and Pashto. The interview was conducted by one researcher, while the other observed and assessed the participant's body language. A transcript of each interview was prepared in the language in which it was conducted (Urdu/Pashto) omitting unwanted details and transcription of all data. This approach ensured that the data collected was accurate and culturally sensitive, respecting the participants' preferences and maintaining the integrity of the research process.

Figure 1

Note: The conceptual framework illustrates how honour killings are rooted in patriarchal systems,

Ethical considerations

The nature of the research is sensitive, and for this reason, it may trigger participants' emotions and harm their mental health. The research followed the guidelines established by the American Psychological Association for ethics, in which a multitude of ethics were considered, to ensure the safety and dignity of the participants. A consent form was given to participants for signing, which included all the necessary information about the research, including its nature, risks, and benefits. Furthermore, a right of withdrawal was provided without any adverse consequences. Since a comprehensive debriefing was conducted, there could be no element of deception. The participants were assured that their demographic information would be kept confidential as well. To conclude, preventing psychological harm was a priority, which was accomplished by instructing participants to take their time when answering questions that might evoke stress, as well as designing questions that were neutral.

Analysis Scheme

The data were analysed using the step of thematic analysis. Following the transcription of data, the data were coded and categorized into themes. It involved the identification of patterns and connections within the data to gain a deeper insight into the research topic. The analysis was conducted iteratively, with themes being refined and revised as new insights emerged

with family enforcement acting as the mechanism through which patriarchal norms

and values are imposed. The thematic analysis identifies key codes such as patriarchal violence, family honour, cultural norms and pressures, legal and community factors, personal agency, mental health, cultural narratives, and gender dynamics. These themes contribute to the understanding of how honour-based violence is justified and sustained within certain sociocultural contexts. The framework connects the act of honour killing to three theoretical

foundations: Cultural Relativism (Franz Boas, early 20th century), which explains how such practices are often justified within cultural contexts; Honour-Based Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979), which explores how group identity and honour influence behavior; and Moral Disengagement (Bandura, 1999), which describes the psychological mechanisms that allow individuals to commit harmful acts without self-condemnation

Results

The analysis of the data revealed several insights into the psychosocial factors because of honor killing in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 1

Thematic findings of participants responses about Patriarchal Violence Family Honour as a major theme (n=14)

Major Theme	Sub theme	Responses in terms of coding	Verbatim	
			Female	Male
Patriarchal Violence Honour	Violating cultural norms Family	Remarriage and Autonomy Marital Affair Deception and Secrecy	<i>Usska janaza aisay nahi hua jaisey aik aam aurat ka hota hai izzat sey</i>	<i>Dono shaadi shuda thay toh dono ney plan banaya keh woh larki keh shohar ko maar day</i>
		Enmity among tribes Family honour based violence	<i>Jenay kor wala na manale rishtay la ao myenz ke dushmani wa</i>	<i>Alak kor wala na manale rishtay la ao myenz ke dushmani wa</i>
		Target killing Couple eloped	<i>Jenay driver sara takhtedale wa ao target killer bande dwara owishtal</i>	
		Secret meeting Pre-marital relationships	<i>Jenay da shpey time ke cha sara milawedo la tale wa ao da de mama zwey qatal ka</i>	

Table 1 highlights Patriarchal Violence as the central theme. Sub-themes include violations of cultural norms, family honour, tribal enmity, and secret relationships. Verbatim responses reflect gendered and cultural perceptions of honor, offering insight into the social context surrounding such incidents.

Table 2

Thematic findings of participants responses about cultural pressure and Resistance, Change, Legal, Social and Community Factors and Personal Agency as a major Theme (n=14)

Major Themes	Sub themes	Responses in terms of coding	Verbatim	
			Females	Males
Cultural Norms and Pressures		Cultural Pressure Protection of Family Honour Conformity to Tradition	<i>Larkiyoun sey expectations hoti hein. Larkiyoun ko highlight kiya jata hai. In ko lagta hai keh larki thori kamzoor hoti hai</i>	
	Maintaining Cultural Expectations	Historical Practices and Traditional Roles Social Control Strong Values	<i>Woh kehtay hein keh bas tum ney yeh kam kiya hai aur humaray khandaan ko badnaam kiya hai phir unkeh traditions keh mutabiq unko saza mili hai</i>	
		Compromised honour Extreme value for Respect Jigra System		<i>Jagaray da para hujray kayba khamakha keni o khabaray ba kege</i>
		Strict rules Social Judgment		<i>Izzat ya namoos da dey beshak jenay we ya alak, khyal limits ao boundaries pejani ao da koranay khyal sati</i>
Legal, Social and Community Factors		Police Negligence Cover up and Denial Community Isolation	<i>Mein nahi manti keh loug itna jaldi claim ker lein gein keh waqai hum ney kisi ka murder kiya hai. Sab sey pehlay toh woh kahein gein keh acha yeh bemaar thi yah isska koi accident ho gaya</i>	<i>Agar woh uss area ki police hai toh woh uss cheez ko slide ker dein gein keh nahi bas izzat keh upper baat aa gayi thi toh maar diya</i>
	Barriers to justice and support	Not supportive community Social ostracism	<i>Mashara uss time per kahaan hota hai jab in keh point of view</i>	<i>Badnaam ho gaya hai toh in sey associate nahi kerna verna loug humaray baray</i>

		judgment	<i>ko izzat nahi di jaati hai</i>	<i>mein bhi bura sochnay lag jayein gein</i>
		Legal protection Close circle account	<i>Da pa zamunga family ke shawe dai</i>	
Resistance, Change and Personal Agency	Breaking free from traditions	Self-awareness Aspiration for change Generational change Resistance to norms Need for education Pride in aiding a girls escape		<i>I have to be a better person aur mein apnay bachoun ko iss tarhaan influence ker sakoon.</i> <i>Ap ney iss cheez per education kaafi deni hoti hai especially in logoun ko kyun keh yeh Islam keh around ghomtay hein toh Islam keh through hi inko prove kerna hota hai keh yeh zada bara gunnah hai kisi ki jaan lena</i>
		Self-independent Respect for personal autonomy Educational awareness	<i>Itna khud mukhtaar banayein keh woh kisi aur keh aagay haath na phela sakein</i>	

Table 2 highlights conformity to traditional norms and stereotypes. The key themes include strict traditional expectations, social judgment, and lack of legal support. Despite these pressures, participants expressed a desire for change through education, personal autonomy, and resistance to harmful norms.

Table 3

Thematic findings of participants responses about impact on mental health (n=14)

Major Themes	Sub themes	Responses in terms of coding	Verbatim	
			Females	Males

Mental Health and Emotional Consequences	Psychological and Emotional Toll	Adverse Mental Health Consequences Bad Mental Health Consequences Emotional Impact	Unko taanay miltay hein keh ap ka yeh wala rishtedaar toh aesay aesay bhaag gaya hai	Pakhpala soch oka Che kama jenay pa ghairat nama qatal ki nu aghay runra ao khwendey senga taqleef ke ba wi
		Internalizing norms Torture Fear	When her mother found out how her daughter had been killed, she was obviously very upset and her mother died a day after her daughter's funeral	
		Humiliation Silence of society Isolation		Masharay keh loug uss time kahaan hotay hein jab ap per sakht waqt ata hai, yeh loug kahein bhi nahi hotay
		Mental health burden Social learning theory	Yao mashum e agha ugori Che zama mashar wror katal uko nu bya agha mashum ba feel kai che za badmash khandan na razama	
Honour killing justifications and Cultural narratives		Honour and family autonomy Pride in honour killing	KPK mein iss per buhat gharoor aur fakhar kiya jata hai keh hum ney unko maar diya	
		Violence normalized as pride No concept of honour killing in religion Violation of religious rules		Woh issko justify aesay kertay hein keh hum associate nahi kertay iss decision sey toh we will just kill them
		Conditional thinking Moral correction		If I'm doing what I know is right aur Allah agar khush hai toh I don't care loug kya kehtay hein uss keh baray mein

Table 3 highlights the psychological impact of honour killings, including fear, trauma, and social isolation. Cultural justifications and distorted religious beliefs further deepen emotional distress and normalize violence.

Table 4

Thematic findings of participants responses about gender dynamic (n=14)

Major Themes	Sub themes	Responses in terms of coding	Verbatim	
			Females	Males
Gender Dynamics		Female Autonomy Male Companionship	<i>Da jinako ao da alakano sara dosti wi ya gupshup nu dasy khabaro bandy</i>	
	Control over gendered roles	Gender differences Superiority complex in Boys Stereotypical gendered norms Traditional roles and norms Patriarchal norms No autonomy Restriction on women mobility	<i>Larkoun ko aesay lagta hai keh yeh mera haq hai, mein aesa ker sakta hoon</i> <i>Aur agar larki ney kuch kiya bhi na ho aur uss per ilzam laga lein toh bas woh badnaam ho jaati hai</i>	

Table 4 highlights gender-based differences, showing how male dominance and traditional norms restrict female autonomy. Participants noted societal double standards and the unequal consequences faced by women.

Discussion

The people of KPK highly value family honour, protecting women, family reputations, and respect. A culture that began over 5000 years ago continues to follow traditional roles and practices today. There are numerous cultural rules, customs, practices, rituals, traditions, festivals, languages, poetry, music, writing, quotes, education, religion, philosophy, discipline, and knowledge passed down through generations that they adhere to. Both negative and positive practices are included in this analysis

KPK has its social norms, which are strictly adhered to by everyone in the community and may have adverse consequences. In terms of the causes of honour killing, it was found that

premarital relationships, unfaithful spouses, love marriages, land disputes, and other factors that contribute to a tarnished family reputation are regarded in a negative light. The effects of these events create an imbalance in the equilibrium of society and are harmful to mental health, particularly for children who are exposed to extreme fear and distress.

A common misconception about honour killing victims is that there is a gender difference. Many interviews indicate that males are also victims, which contradicts the commonly held assumption that victims are females. In terms of the rules imposed on men and women, there are gender differences, with men having a more powerful voice in certain aspects of life than women, such as a later curfew.

Those who commit honour killings and their families leave behind suffer great psychological distress. Women and men break social and cultural norms to preserve the dignity of their families according to this practice. There has been a decline in such practices in recent years, but parents still shoot or kill their children in some parts of Pakistan.

In the results, women and men were severely punished if they departed from the cultural norms, such as rejecting arranged marriages, but there was still a degree of gender disparity found. According to one research participant 'Agar larki ko larka pasand aa jaye aur wo ghalti karay phir unko maar diya jata hai. Pathanoun mein issi baat ko ghairat samjhtay hein aur qatal ker detay hein'. A statement such as this highlights the deeply ingrained inequalities and double standards that are embedded within the fabric of our society. This story illustrates how girls face severe punishment, frequently death, for expressing their preferences in romantic relationships or for acting in a way that is perceived as violating cultural norms, all in the interest of preserving ghairat (honour). A Pathan cultural code in this instance legitimates violent reactions by viewing female autonomy as a threat to family or tribal honour.

In order to provide a further perspective on the issue at hand, additional verbatims were selected. The narrative was narrated by a male participant, "Disay kho pa pakistan kai su rules nishta say ko tu bya Pashtuns ta ogoray nu bya har tribes khpal rules rowalee" which means that different tribes bring about their own rules and regulations (often derived by the Pashtunwali/ Code of honour) due to the lack of rules and regulations in Pakistan. Secondly, the same male said "Jinako ta khpal marzi kawal pakar da kho jinako ta khpal limit ke kawal pakar e" which translates to "women can act upon their free will, but they should be doing it within limits" to further explain the rules for women that they are permitted to do certain things however it should be to a certain limit. These particular individual further states "Khalak mungta wai che munga backwards yu asay munga kho shukar obasu che zamunga mor o khor safe e da dai rules da wajay na", that people usually say the Pashtun are

backwards, but we are thankful (to God) that at least our mothers and sisters are safe in their homes due to these rules.

It also showed that no community-based interventions or psychological support are provided if such incidents happen to the grieving families. An individual reported 'Bas police investigation kerti hai, woh toh apnay taraf sey kertay hein lekin jab baray baray loug hotay hein toh bas wo paisey day ker choot jatay hein' which highlights corruption, a more lethal issue than honour killing, allowing the rich and wealthy to escape the legal consequences. It sheds light on the failure of the justice system when it comes to punishing and holding powerful accountable. Lack of psychological support provided by the community is evidenced by 'Agar ghairat keh naam per qatal ho jaye toh unka poora khandaan un sey laa-taluqi ikhtiyaar ker leta hai keh hum bas, humara in sey koi taluq nahi hai.' At such vulnerable times, instead of showing any empathy or support to the grieving families, there is social distancing or disownment by the extended relatives or by the community in general. The family does not only suffer a tragic loss but are also deprived of the emotional comfort they can get from their surroundings, further worsening their trauma.

One limitation that was identified was that no previous existing literature was found on this topic based on this specific region. Addressing this issue requires strict policies to be enforced so that no one takes the law into their hand, no matter what the issue is, a good legal system to provide protection to the individuals, and more awareness, emphasizing individual rights instead of cultural reputation as can be seen in the theory of cultural relativism.

Implications

An examination of honour killings that focuses on the why behind them reveals a multitude of reasons. Specifically, it will be focusing on the benefits it provides to non-governmental organizations in Pakistan, as well as introducing mental health interventions in counselling psychology. The NGO sector plays an essential role in helping to address various issues across Pakistan, however, in order to focus their efforts

on certain aspects, they should be provided with sufficient information. NGOs may develop effective campaigns and support systems for the community in the wake of conducting studies. Additionally, honour killings can leave psychological scars on the victims, their families, and the communities in which they occur. By shedding light on the psychological aspects, this study can help identify and understand the mental health challenges that occur as a result and design effective interventions in counselling psychology. It may also contribute to the world of social psychology and cultural psychology, where deeper understandings could be developed.

Limitations and Recommendations

Drawbacks in qualitative studies are inevitable. For this study, individuals who were approached expressed their concerns regarding their family restrictions and voiced the fact that it was not permissible for them to talk about what they witnessed or heard in their community, limiting the overall deeper insights. Secondly, visiting the remote areas on the outskirts was logically challenging. It was difficult to go there due to the time constraints and the costs of going. Thirdly, the aim of the sample was to interview 20 participants, however saturation was obtained by the time 14 interviews were conducted. Fourthly, the teenage perspective was also missing as our research included individuals aged 20 to 54 years old. A teenage perspective could have further highlighted the root cause of this problem by analysing their thinking patterns and perceptions regarding this topic. The limitations faced by the researchers are the areas that could be improved in future research.

Conclusion

Honour killing, an act often seen as restoring the family honour, is a grave and offensive crime that violates basic human rights. It is deeply rooted in our culture's patriarchal norms, where a family member, usually a woman, is punished for actions that are thought to bring shame to the family, such as choosing her future partner or refusing for arranged marriage. It not only deprives victims of their fundamental rights to life and liberty but also inflicts enduring

psychological trauma on families and communities, frequently stifling dissent and sustaining cycles of fear and oppression. Families are frequently prevented from seeking justice or healing due to the stigma and silence surrounding honour-based violence, which exacerbates their emotional scars. Their voices implore us to unite in our feelings, celebrate the spirit of justice, and create a world where every life is precious and worthy of respect (Rehan, 2024).

A sovereign nation like Pakistan can establish norms, regulations, laws, and cultural frameworks to protect women's rights. The rule of law is crucial for holding criminals accountable, especially in cases of honour killings, a brutal act that constantly violates women's rights under the guise of honour. The practice of honour killing in any religion lacks a rational foundation and should therefore not be tolerated as part of our national legislation. A multidisciplinary response must be taken to tackle the psychological consequences of honour killings, with legal reforms, cultural discussion, and mental health interventions, in hope of safeguarding vulnerable individuals and helping families mourn and break the cycle of violence.

Conflicts of interest: Not present in the current study.

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References

- Ali. R. (2001). *The Dark Side of Honour: Women Victims in Pakistan*. Lahore: Shirkat Gah. Quoted in: "Killing in the Name of Honour: How Pakistan's Laws Fail Women" (April 2025) .
- Cassar, C. (2024). *Franz Boas – The father of American anthropology*. Anthropology Review. <https://anthropologyreview.org/franz-boas-the-father-of-american-anthropology>

- Cohen, D., & Nisbett, R. E. (1994). Self-protection and the culture of honor: Explaining Southern violence. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 20(5), 551-567. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167294205012>
- Haider, S. B. (2024). 'Honour' crimes continued to persist in 2024, threatening Pakistani women's lives. *DAWN.COM*. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1881836>
- Hassan, M. (2024). Exploratory research - Types, methods, and examples. *ResearchMethod.net*. <https://researchmethod.net/exploratory-research/>
- Kanwal, S. (2021). Honor killing: A case study of Pakistan. *Journal of Law & Social Studies*, 3(1), 38-43. <https://doi.org/10.52279/jlss.03.01.3843>
- Lari, M. Z., & Aurat Publication & Information Service Foundation. (2011). *A pilot study on honour killings in Pakistan and compliance of law*. Islamabad: Aurat Foundation. Retrieved from Library of Congress
- Lim, W. M. (2024). What is qualitative research? An overview and guidelines. *SAGE Journals*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211047561>
- Malik, S., Parveen, F., Aziz, A., Rana, F. A., Siddiq, M. S., & Nazir, B. (2023). Honor killing: A socio-psychological phenomenon? *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374697476>
- McLeod, S. (2023). Social identity theory in psychology (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/social-identity-theory.html>
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). What is purposive sampling? Definition & examples. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>
- Pamir, E., Waheedi, A., & Habib, K. A. (2023). Some aspects of Pashtun culture. *Randwick International of Social Science (RISS) Journal*. <https://www.randwickresearch.com/index.php/rissj>
- Rehan, T. (2024). Honour killing in Pakistan: A grim reality. *Paradigm Shift*. <https://www.paradigmshift.com.pk/honour-killing-in-pakistan/>
- Taherdoost, H. (2022). How to conduct an effective interview: A guide to interview design in research study. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356993206>
- Tan, D. E. (2024). Understanding the frustration aggression hypothesis in psychology. *Listen-Hard*. <https://listen-hard.com/psychology/frustration-aggression-hypothesis>
- Wagle, K. (2025). Pilot testing: Importance, steps & challenges. *Public Health Notes*. <https://publichealthnotes.com/pilot-testing-importance-steps-challenges>